

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

TOSHKENT
MENEJMENT VA
IQTISODIYOT
INSTITUTI

**BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH VA
IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH:
MUAMMOLAR, YECHIMLAR VA
XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-
AMALIY ANJUMANI
ILMIY MAQOLALAR VA
TEZISLAR TO'PLAMI

2024-yil 18-oktabr

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**№7-SON
MAXSUS SON**

2
4

Digital
Object
Identifier

74-91 xalqaro daraja

ISSN: 2992-8982

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Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali
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huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori
bilan ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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3-SHO'BA. **MOLIYA VA SOLIQ SOHASIDAGI MUAMMOLAR,** **YECHIMLAR VA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR**

STATE OF PLAY OF GREEN FINANCE IN UZBEKISTAN: OPPORTUNITIES FOR AND BARRIERS TO GREEN BOND ISSUANCE

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Abstract: This article presents the potential role of green bonds in financing Uzbekistan's green transition, the priority sectors for green bond issuance and barriers that potential issuers face. Non-sovereign issuers, notably subnational governments and corporate entities, face barriers in terms of the country's existing regulatory requirements and persistent knowledge and expertise gaps, but there is considerable potential for the use of the instrument to finance these issuers' green projects. Other bond-like instruments, such as green sukuk, an Islamic fixed-income instrument, could prove effective at mobilizing domestic demand and offer an alternative financing mechanism if regulatory hurdles to the development of Islamic finance in Uzbekistan are removed. The energy sector, particularly renewable power generation projects, is the sector with the most potential for green bond issuances, but agriculture, transport, housing and water management projects could benefit as well.

Key words: green economy, green finance, bonds, infrastructure, bond market, energy, transport, agriculture, housing.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yashil obligatsiyalarning O'zbekistonning yashil o'tish davrini moliyalashtirishdagi potentsial roli, ularni chiqarishning ustuvor tarmoqlari va potentsial emitentlar duch keladigan to'siqlar ko'rsatilgan. Suveren bo'lmagan emitentlar, xususan, submilliy hukumatlar va korporativ tuzilmalar mamlakatning mavjud tartibga soluvchi talablari va doimiy bilim va tajriba bo'shliqlari bilan bog'liq to'siqlarga duch kelishadi. Biroq, ushbu emitentlarning yashil loyihalarini moliyalashtirishda ushbu vositadan foydalanish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud. Obligatsiyalarga o'xshash boshqa vositalar, masalan, islomning qat'iy daromadli vositasi bo'lgan yashil sukuk, agar O'zbekistonda islom moliyasini rivojlantirish yo'lidagi me'yoriy to'siqlar bartaraf etilsa, ichki talabni safarbar qilish va muqobil moliyalashtirish mexanizmini taklif qilishda samarali bo'lishi mumkin. Energetika sektori, xususan, qayta tiklanadigan energiya loyihalari yashil obligatsiyalarni chiqarish uchun eng katta salohiyatga ega, ammo qishloq xo'jaligi, transport, uy-joy va suv xo'jaligidagi loyihalar ham foyda keltirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, yashil moliya, obligatsiyalar, infratuzilma, obligatsiyalar bozori, energetika, transport, qishloq xo'jaligi, uy-joy.

Аннотация: В этой статье представлена потенциальная роль зеленых облигаций в финансировании зеленого перехода Узбекистана, приоритетные сектора для их выпуска и барьеры, с которыми сталкиваются потенциальные эмитенты. Несуверенные эмитенты, в частности субнациональные правительства и корпоративные субъекты, сталкиваются с барьерами, связанными с существующими нормативными требованиями страны и сохраняющимися пробелами в знаниях и опыте. Однако существует значительный потенциал для использования этого инструмента в финансировании зеленых проектов этих эмитентов. Другие инструменты, аналогичные облигациям, такие как зеленые сукук — исламский инструмент с фиксированным доходом, могут оказаться эффективными для мобилизации внутреннего спроса и предложить альтернативный механизм финансирования, если будут устранены нормативные препятствия для развития исламского финансирования в Узбекистане. Энергетический сектор, в частности проекты по производству возобновляемой энергии, имеет наибольший потенциал для выпуска зеленых облигаций, но проекты в области сельского хозяйства, транспорта, жилищного строительства и управления водными ресурсами также могут извлечь выгоду.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, зеленое финансирование, облигации, инфраструктура, рынок облигаций, энергетика, транспорт, сельское хозяйство, жилье.

INTRODUCTION

Bonds are a potential solution to one of the major barriers to the financing of some sustainable infrastructure: maturity mismatch. Infrastructure projects, and particularly sustainable infrastructure projects, are characterized by high up-front capital costs and long-dated income streams. Unlike direct financing from banks and corporate entities, bonds can provide longer-term debt capital to finance infrastructure projects or refinance shorter-term loans at potentially more beneficial terms. Although they hardly offer a 'silver bullet' solution to the financing

gap, bonds can complement other forms of infrastructure financing for long-term capital-intensive projects¹.

DATA ANALYSIS

Uzbekistan could choose to finance infrastructure projects using conventional (or 'vanilla') bonds, which have looser restrictions on the use of proceeds by the issuer. However, green bonds, part of a wider ecosystem of thematic bonds, including green, social and sustainability bonds, have a few distinct advantages for Uzbekistan as it seeks to finance its green transition. Like conventional bonds, thematic bonds are debt instruments issued by governments (sovereign bonds) or banks, other corporate entities or supranational institutions (corporate bonds) that offer regular payments at a fixed interest rate (coupon rate) to debt holders until the bond reaches maturity. They differ from traditional 'vanilla' bonds in that, in the case of green, social and sustainability bonds, the use of their proceeds is restricted to green projects, social projects or a mix of green and social projects (for sustainability bonds)².

Although these restrictions make the issuance of thematic bond more complicated since the proceeds need to be ring fenced and their use and impact carefully monitored and reported, the assurance they provide about the use of proceeds make them particularly attractive to investors with ESG portfolio requirements. Among investors there is a growing awareness that non-financial sustainability risks could have a significant impact on risk-adjusted returns in the long term, and they therefore seek investments with lower exposure to climate-related and other ESG risks. Several jurisdictions, including Brazil, Canada, the EU, New Zealand, Switzerland, the UK and the USA, have already made climate risk disclosures mandatory for some financial institutions, and other markets, including China, India and Japan, are expected to follow suit³. Growing consumer demand has led to a rapid expansion of the global sustainable finance market. Across five major financial markets (Australia and New Zealand, Canada, Europe, Japan and the United States), total sustainable assets increased by 30% between 2016 and the end of 2019 to reach USD 30 trillion. Sustainable funds have expanded their assets under management globally, nearing USD 1 trillion in 2019, with 75% held by institutional investors and 25% by retail investors⁴. By offering financial instruments like green bonds, which are designed to guarantee low climate risk exposure and meaningful impact on environmental criteria, Uzbekistan's government or other potential Uzbekistan-based issuers could tap into an additional source of financing.

Figure 1. **Issuances of sovereign thematic bonds and sustainability-linked bonds in emerging markets have accelerated sharply in recent years** (Billion USD, pre-2016, 2016-22 and January-September 2023.)⁵

Globally, the sovereign thematic bond market – as well as the market for sustainability-linked bonds – has developed rapidly in recent years, with record issuance of USD 1 151 billion in 2021, over half of which was strictly green⁶. Emerging countries are small but growing players in the market (see Figure 1), accounting

1 OECD (2017), *Mobilizing Bond Markets for a Low-Carbon Transition*, OECD, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/24090344> (accessed on 28 June 2023).

2 OECD (2021), *Scaling up Green, Social, Sustainability and Sustainability-linked Bond Issuances in Developing Countries*, OECD, Paris, [https://one.oecd.org/document/DCD\(2021\)20/En/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/DCD(2021)20/En/pdf) (accessed on 27 June 2023).

3 Jonson, E. (2022), *The Complete Guide to National Climate-Related Disclosures*, Carbon Cloud, <https://carboncloud.com/2022/09/08/mandatory-climate-disclosures/> (accessed on 28 June 2023).

4 OECD (2020), *OECD Business and Finance Outlook 2020: Sustainable and Resilient Finance*, OECD, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/eb61fd29-en> (accessed on 28 June 2023).

5 Source: World Bank (2023[11]), "Green, Social, Sustainability, and Sustainability-linked (GSSS) Bonds Market Update October 2023", <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/3d313e4819de8d6bcb4238f253874b0f-0340012023/original/GSSS-Quarterly-Newsletter-Issue-No-5.pdf>.

6 World Bank (2022), *Sovereign Green, Social and Sustainability Bonds: Unlocking the Potential for Emerging Markets and Devel-*

for about 15% of total issuance volume. Financial (41%) and corporate entities (37%) have issued the bulk of such bonds, while national governments (13%) and subnational governments, government agencies and development banks (8%) account for most of the remainder. Most emerging market bond issuances have been placed on international exchanges (76%) and in hard currency like USD, EUR and JPY (74% of bond issuances and 76% by volume).

A World Bank survey of 32 sovereign issuers of thematic and sustainability-linked bonds revealed that the main motivation behind their choice of a thematic rather than a conventional bond issuance was the desire to diversify their investor base. Other most-cited motivations were to signal commitment to sustainability and raise the funding needed for sustainable investments.

Potential types of green bond issuance. Sovereign bonds - across emerging markets, both countries eligible for official development assistance (ODA) and those that are not, corporate thematic bond issuances have predominated to date. However, among ODA-eligible countries like Uzbekistan, public sector issuances – mostly sovereign bonds – account for over half of issuances. Given the size of governments' budgets and the role sovereign issuances play in providing benchmarking instruments for local market development, sovereign issuers are well placed to promote the development of a national thematic bond market. As such, the fact that initial forays into thematic bond financing in Uzbekistan have been led by the government in the form of sovereign bonds is in line with its peer ODA-eligible countries.

Although Uzbekistan's first (conventional) sovereign bond issuance dates only from 2019, it has been quick to experiment with sovereign thematic bonds. In November 2020, Uzbekistan offered a two-tranche bond (a so-called "development finance institution (DFI) bond") consisting of a 10-year USD 555 million tranche and a 3-year UZS 2 trillion tranche. The bond attracted a broad base of investors resulting in an oversubscription ratio of 2.5. A portion of the DFI bond's proceeds are benefiting several development projects relevant to social Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including the construction of schools (SDG 4), health institutions (SDG 3), potable water and sewage pipelines (SDG 6) as well as roads (SDG 9). It also funds social welfare programmes to support women (SDG 5), children and the unemployed (SDGs 1 and 8)⁷.

In July 2021, Uzbekistan issued its first sovereign thematic bond (a so-called "SDG bond"), a sustainability bond aimed at supporting social and climate-related SDGs (SDGs 1-9, 11, 13 and 15). In preparation for the SDG Bond issuance, the government of Uzbekistan developed the SDG Bond Framework with support from the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). Sustainalytics provided a second-party opinion on the Framework finding it to be in alignment with the Sustainability Bond Guidelines 2021, Green Bond Principles 2021 and Social Bond Principles 2021. Given its alignment with international standards on thematic bonds, the SDG Bond Framework can also be used to issue green bonds, and in October 2023 a second sovereign thematic bond – this time a green bond – was issued⁸.

Corporate bonds. To date, all of Uzbekistan's corporate bond issuances have been carried out by SOEs (see above) or state-owned banks, namely the National Bank of Uzbekistan, Sanoa tQurilish Bank (SQB) and Ipoteka Bank. The government plans to privatize these latter two in the coming years, although privatization has been delayed by unstable market conditions. Given the government's stated priority to attract domestic and international capital through green bonds, Uzbekistan's state-owned banks are increasingly interested in organizing issuances. In November 2022, the OECD organized a 2-day peer-learning workshop between representatives of SQB, one of Uzbekistan's largest state-owned banks, and America bank, a leading Armenian bank that has emerged as a pioneer in the adoption of green bonds in the region of Eastern Europe, the Caucasus and Central Asia. Many large state-owned banks in Uzbekistan, which account for most of the country's banking sector, are slated for privatization in the coming years and are increasingly interested in debt instruments as they will come to rely more on markets than state subsidies. Banks do not face the same legislative and regulatory constraints as other potential issuers such as subnational governments, but instead lack practical expertise in developing and using debt instruments and particularly thematic bonds, which require stronger transparency, monitoring and compliance mechanisms. Peer-learning exercises between banks and especially banks operating in financial ecosystems with similar challenges and levels of development can help develop capacity and identify opportunities to adopt green bonds and other financial instruments.

The developing market for green mortgages in Uzbekistan could offer another opportunity for green bond issuances. These mortgages, primarily provided by Qishloq Qurilish Bank and Ipoteka Bank, offer lower rates for homes designed to reduce water and energy consumption. These banks, as well as the Uzbekistan

oping Economies, World Bank, <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/4de3839b85c57eb958dd207fad132f8e-0340012022/original/WB-GSS-Bonds-Survey-Report.pdf> (accessed on 27 June 2023).

7 OECD (2017), Mobilising Bond Markets for a Low-Carbon Transition, OECD, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/24090344> (accessed on 28 June 2023).

8 Ministry of Economy and Finance (2023), The Republic of Uzbekistan for the first time placed "green" international bonds in the national currency, <https://www.imv.uz/en/news/category/yangiliklar/post-1621>

Mortgage Refinancing Company, could develop green mortgage-backed bonds in the domestic capital market.

Sukuks. One Islamic financial instrument of particular interest is the sukuk, a Shariah-compliant fixed-income instrument comparable to a bond. Unlike bonds, sukuks do not pay interest, which is prohibited under Islamic law, but instead offer a comparable stream of payments over a fixed maturity period in the form of profit or rent. To achieve this, broadly speaking, sukuks represent partial ownership of real tangible assets or a contract with an underlying entity, although the ownership and payments cease once the instrument achieves maturity. Sukuks can be structured according to several different contracts, including lease sukuks and principal-agency sukuks, the two most commonly used structures in green sukuks. The choice of structure depends on factors such as the nature of the underlying assets, tax and regulatory considerations, tradability considerations, the return (fixed or floating), the type of issuer (sovereign or corporate), the targeted investor base and the Sharia approach of the scholars who approve the sukuk issue. In all cases, proceeds from sukuks, like green bonds, cannot be used to finance certain activities. In the case of conventional sukuks, excluded activities include alcohol and pork production; under a green sukuk, additional exclusionary criteria for environmentally harmful activities and eligibility criteria for green products are included⁹.

Sukuks, like bonds, can be issued by sovereign or corporate entities, and they can be conventional or thematic, including green, social, sustainability and sustainability-linked sukuks. Following Malaysia's first issuance in 2017, the market has expanded rapidly (see Figure 2). Most issuances have occurred in Indonesia (27%), Malaysia (20%), Saudi Arabia (13%) and the United Arab Emirates (8%), with supranational institutions (24%), notably the Islamic Development Bank, accounting for a large share as well. Central Asian countries have so far been absent from the green sukuk market, although the Development Bank of Kazakhstan issued a conventional sukuk in 2012 and the Astana International Finance Centre has been positioning itself as an Islamic finance hub, offering Islamic financial products and services in Kazakhstan since 2018 and attracting a cross-listing of a sukuk issued by the Qatar International Islamic Bank. Uzbekistan could stand to benefit from the expertise of these countries' institutions as it seeks to facilitate the adoption of green sukuks.

Figure 2. The market for green, social, sustainability and sustainability-linked sukuks has expanded more than tenfold since 2017

(Green, social, sustainability and sustainability-linked sukuk issuances in million USD, 2017-21 and the first half of 2022.)¹⁰

International institutions are supporting the government of Uzbekistan in its efforts, expressed in its Program for Capital Market Development 2021-2023, to create the necessary regulatory and market conditions for the introduction of Islamic finance and green sukuks. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and the Islamic Development Bank have launched a technical assistance project aimed at developing relevant legislative

9 Refinitiv (2022), Financing a Sustainable Future: Green and Sustainability Sukuk Report 2022, Refinitiv, https://www.refinitiv.com/content/dam/marketing/en_us/documents/gated/reports/green-sustainability-sukuk-report-2022.pdf

10 Source: Refinitiv (2022[19]), Green and sustainability sukuk report 2022, https://www.refinitiv.com/content/dam/marketing/en_us/documents/gated/reports/green-sustainability-sukuk-report-2022.pdf.

and regulatory framework as well as to elaborate the National Green Sukuk Framework for Uzbekistan. The UNDP, the Ministry of Finance (now the Ministry of Economy and Finance), the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD) and Ansher Capital LLC delivered a webinar in 2022 aimed at raising awareness and interest in Islamic finance instruments and determining priority areas for further work.

Conclusions and Recommendations. Thematic bonds, such as green, social and sustainability bonds, and thematic sukuk are potentially useful instruments for financing part of Uzbekistan's green transition, and certain sectors, due to their high share in Uzbekistan's greenhouse gas emissions and the market-ready nature of the projects they can offer, are particularly good candidates for early exploration of the instrument's potential.

The most critical sector is energy, as it has the greatest environmental impact and consequently the largest potential for the implementation of projects related to the transition. The transport, agriculture, housing and water sectors can also be identified as areas with vast potential for promoting a green economy, as a number of green projects have been launched and implemented in the areas of construction and water management.

Energy: In Uzbekistan's natural gas-dominated energy sector, the renewable energy market growing more attractive to investors thanks in part to government support and incentive programs. By 2030, Uzbekistan plans to diversify its power generation system, integrating more solar photovoltaic plants (8%) and wind power plants (7%). With maturing renewable markets globally and strengthening mandates for investors to invest in environmental, social and governance (ESG) compliant financial products, Uzbekistan's public and soon-to-be private institutions could package market-ready renewable electricity projects into attractive debt market instruments. Energy efficiency projects, notably in the country's housing sector, could also contribute to a bond's project portfolio. Both types of projects were already included in Uzbekistan's sovereign SDG bond issuance, demonstrating their viability.

Transport: Uzbekistan's government has made the domestic production and uptake of electric vehicles a priority for the green development of the transport sector. UzAuto Motors, one of the two SOEs to have issued a bond in Uzbekistan to date, and other vehicle manufacturing companies in Uzbekistan could contribute to the government's electric vehicle push and diversify their financing sources by issuing green bonds based on projects for development of the sector.

Agriculture: Agriculture employs about a quarter of Uzbekistan's population, and the sector is important for both domestic food supply and exports. A number of environmental concerns, including water management and biodiversity loss, remain to be addressed, and some aspects of the sector's green transition could be financed through green bond issuances. Projects to improve water supply, which is currently conducted through an extensive and inefficient grid of dams, canals and pumping stations, and irrigation as well as introduce sustainable methods of farming, pasturing and waste management, could be eligible for inclusion in green bond issuances from the government, banks or relevant corporate entities.

Housing: A nascent market for green mortgages exists in Uzbekistan, whereby banks are beginning to offer lower rates for homes designed to reduce water and energy consumption. Although banks currently face regulatory restrictions against issuing mortgage-backed securities, banks and the Uzbekistan Mortgage Refinancing Company could develop mortgage-backed green bonds in the future.

Water supply and sanitation: Uzbekistan already included a number of water supply and sanitation projects in its first sovereign SDG bond issuance. Similar approaches could be taken for sub-sovereign bond issuances, provided that legislative and regulatory barriers are removed.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokr ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 7-maxsus son

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

